

Research article

Robust optimization of the energy concept of an industrial process w.r.t. uncertain energy costs and environmental conditions

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ABSTRACT

In order to limit the global warming to 1.5 °C as decided by the Paris Agreement, the greenhouse gas emissions have to be dramatically reduced within the next couple of years. In order to realize this in industrial sectors with low to medium temperature requirements, such as food or pulp and paper industry, fossil fuels must be replaced by renewable energy sources to generate electricity, steam and process heat. To realize this in a most economical way, a deterministic multi-objective optimization and a robust scalar optimization of the renewable energy concept of an industrial process are carried out, whereby the robust optimization takes uncertainties in the assumptions of the price for purchasing natural gas and the solar radiation into account. To set up the automated optimization processes, suitable mathematical descriptions of generation units (e.g. photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, solar thermal systems), conversion units (e.g. heat pumps, boilers) and storages (e.g. thermal, electrical) are described first. The comparison of both optimization approaches shows that deterministic optimization is able to find very good solutions, but that the spread of the objectives is significantly larger than with robust optimization when there are uncertainties in the assumptions. The robust optimization thus expands the portfolio for selecting suitable energy concepts and enables future scenarios and developments to be considered, which is particularly necessary in dynamic and heavily changing environments. Furthermore, considering the typically long operating times of industrial plants, economically well-founded decisions can be made, which can have a positive effect on the current restraint to make necessary investments..

1. Introduction

Essentially, CO₂ emissions in the industry can be divided into two areas: energy related emissions mainly caused by burning fossil fuels to generate electricity, process heat, steam and mechanical work; and process related emissions caused by non-energy use of carbon-based raw materials, IRENA (2024). The studies in this work are focused to reduce energy related emissions from industrial processes with temperature requirements of less than 200 °C, such as e.g. in the food or paper industry. However, the approaches presented can also be transferred to other industries. For a successful decarbonization of such industrial processes it is essential to integrate renewable energies in an appropriate way in the energy concept considering economic as well as environmental aspects, Mitsos et al. (2018). For this purpose, it is necessary to model the required units (generation, conversion, storage) sufficiently to gain an understanding of their interaction and characteristics. Finally, it is necessary to determine the most suitable units from the large number of units available and to dimension them accordingly. Due to the large number of possibilities, a manual determination is difficult to realize and will mostly end up in sub-optimal energy concepts so that numerical optimizations are therefore increasingly being used.

1.1. Optimization of energy concepts

With the increasing complexity of investigated energy concepts and the associated number of parameters (number and dimension of units), optimization processes are increasingly being applied, Langiu et al. (2021). This includes almost all industrial areas in which designs and systems are consistently pushed to the limits of feasibility. Thus, the need for design and operational optimizations of energy concepts for industrial processes is also increasing due to the global economic competition and increasing political and social pressure to reduce CO₂ emissions. The design of an energy concept is typically formulated as mixed integer nonlinear problem, where the dimension or capacity of the units is described by a real number whereas with the integer variable defines the number of units used, Voll et al. (2013). In the context of this paper, the units used are specified, so that the complexity of the optimization problem can be reduced, while still using nonlinear modeling of the units, Fig. 1. A more accurate unit modeling is usually used for operational optimizations involving e.g. non-linear model predictive control with real-time weather data or forecasts, Sass et al.

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Nomenclature**Latin symbols**

A	area [m^2]
C	capital expenditures [€]
c	constant, specific heat [kJ (kg K)^{-1}]
E	energy [kWh]
f	performance, uncertainty factor [-]
g	specific global warming index [$\text{gCO}_2\text{eq (kWh)}^{-1}$]
\dot{m}	mass flow rate [kg (s)^{-1}]
m	mass [kg]
P	power [kW], probability, quantile [-]
p	specific price [€ ($\text{kWh})^{-1}$]
\mathbf{p}	parameter vector [-]
Q	thermal energy [kWh]
\dot{Q}	thermal power [kW]
S	solar radiation [$\text{kWh (m}^2\text{)}^{-1}$]
T	temperature [K]

Greek symbols

α	maintenance factor
β	panel tilt angle, interest rate
δ	declination angle of the sun
η	efficiency
γ	scaling exponent
λ	load fraction
τ	time horizon
φ	latitude of industrial site

Subscripts and superscripts

d	daily
det	deterministic
hor	horizontal
in	inlet
inc	incidence
nom	nominal
out	output
pen	penal
rob	robust

Abbreviations

EB	electric boiler
GB	gas boiler
GWI	global warming index
HP	heat pump
PV	photovoltaic unit
ST	solar thermal unit
TAC	total annual cost
TES	thermal energy storage
WT	wind turbine unit

(2020). Such a complex operational optimization is not carried out here, but a simplified operational optimization is needed to determine the operating costs, which results in a two-level optimization problem, Fossli et al. (2023). However, stationary modeling of the components is often sufficient for the design optimization of an energy concept. In general, as part of the optimization of energy concepts, assumptions are

made about the costs and performance of the units, prices for natural gas and electricity and environmental conditions such as wind speeds and solar radiation. However, these assumptions can change over the course of the usually long operating period, so that large deviations from the original assumptions can arise, particularly in terms of operating costs. To avoid this, usually only selected scenarios, Majewski et al. (2017), of safety factors, Andiappan (2017), are considered in current energy concept design processes. In order to define relevant scenarios, an appropriate selection must also be made. A probabilistic consideration of a large number of possible scenarios does not currently take place in energy concept designs.

1.2. Robust optimization strategies

Optimized systems often only behave ideally under the given boundary conditions and deviations can lead to undesired system behavior or a loss of performance. The goal of a robust optimization is to consider uncertainties or deviations already during design optimization process. There are many definitions regarding robustness, like a small scatter in the objectives or low failure probabilities, Keane and Nair (2005). For each of the defined robust criteria there are sophisticated methods for their efficient estimation. In any case, the consideration of conditions away from the design point requires a number of function evaluations to determine the robust objectives. However, response surface methods in connection with robust optimizations are often very suitable, which can be created on the basis of a few function evaluations and then used to carry out extensive statistical evaluations efficiently, Dellino et al. (2010).

1.3. Objective and structure of the paper

In this paper, the robust optimization methodology is combined and applied in an exemplary manner with the optimization of an energy concept to demonstrate the advantages of directly integrating uncertainties into the design. Local response surfaces are used for the evaluation of the robust objectives, which are created around the nominal energy concept design in every design evaluation. By the comparison with a deterministic optimization, the advantages and possible applications of robust optimization are described.

In the following section, firstly the mathematical modeling of the units under consideration is described and the corresponding analysis of the entire energy concept is explained, Fig. 1. An electrical battery is not directly considered in this paper, but since the energy balances are calculated on a daily basis, it is assumed that the corresponding amount of electricity can be stored for a short time. The unit modeling serves as the basis for the energy concept optimization process, in which the nominal capacities of the units are optimized. Finally, the robust optimization problem is presented and its solution is compared with a deterministic optimum.

2. Methodology of the energy concept modeling

In order to design and dimension the units shown in Fig. 1, it is necessary to model them by an energetic point of view. The modeling then forms the basis for determining the electrical energy and heat produced in order to cover the production needs at all times. For this purpose, the formulations of the generation, conversion and storage units are first described in the following sections before the evaluation of the overall system is explained.

Fig. 1. Overview of the energy concept to be optimized showing the electricity, gas and heating grid.

2.1. Generation units

The output of the generation units essentially depends on the installed capacity, solar radiations and wind speeds. The installed capacity is described by the area of the panels for the PV and ST units and by the nominal power for the wind turbine. The electrical power P^{PV} provided by the PV unit is thus calculated according to Sass et al. (2020) by

$$P^{PV} = A^{PV} \eta^{PV} S^{pan} \quad (1)$$

with the panel area A^{PV} , panel efficiency η^{PV} and solar radiation S^{pan} which summarizes direct and diffuse radiations. The electrical power is limited by the nominal capacity P_{nom}^{PV} , such that

$$P^{PV} \leq P_{nom}^{PV} \quad \text{with} \quad P_{nom}^{PV} = A^{PV} P_{nom,rel}^{PV} = A^{PV} 0.171. \quad (2)$$

Values for solar radiation are taken from monthly totals S_{M}^{hor} for a horizontal surface for the region of the industrial site from the German weather service, DWD (2023). Using the geometric relationships in Fig. 2a, the corresponding solar radiation S^{inc} of the sun can be determined using its declination angle δ as well as the latitude φ of the industrial site:

$$S^{inc} = \frac{S^{hor}}{\sin \alpha} \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = 90^\circ - \varphi + \delta. \quad (3)$$

A tilt angle β of the PV module then corresponds to a decrease in latitude φ , so that the solar radiation on the module is calculated by

$$S^{pan} = S^{inc} \sin(\alpha + \beta) = S^{hor} \frac{\sin(\alpha + \beta)}{\sin \alpha}. \quad (4)$$

The efficiency of the PV unit was chosen with $\eta^{PV} = 0.09$ in such a way that calculated values correspond to the measurements of a PV unit already installed at the industrial site.

The electrical power provided by the wind turbine unit is determined by the nominal power P_{nom}^{WT} and a wind load fraction λ^{WT} dependent efficiency η^{WT} :

$$P^{WT} = \eta^{WT}(\lambda^{WT}) P_{nom}^{WT} \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda^{WT} = \frac{v^{wind}}{v^{wind,0}} \quad (5)$$

where a reference wind speed of $v^{wind,0} = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is chosen for the present study. Due to the linear dependency in (5), only a single representative wind turbine unit is considered at this point, a separation

into several wind turbines with different capacities does not take place here. The efficiency function is selected according to Sass et al. (2020)

$$\eta^{WT}(\lambda^{WT}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda^{WT} < 0.33 \\ 1.5393\lambda^{WT} - 0.5091 & \text{if } 0.33 \leq \lambda^{WT} \leq 1.0 \\ 1 & \text{if } \lambda^{WT} > 1.0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

and displayed Fig. 2b. The wind speeds used here are taken from measurements at the industrial site. The same distributions of wind speeds and thus the same output of the wind turbine unit is assumed for each day in this paper. A distinction between days with a lot and little wind does not take place for the design of the wind turbine unit.

To determine the output of the solar thermal unit, a single equivalent solar panel is usually considered, for which the inlet and outlet temperatures w.r.t a given mass flow are calculated, Debulac et al. (2021). However, to find an appropriate design an optimization of the mass flow in the panels is required, which may necessary for an operational consideration, but not for the design. For the design, the calculation of the thermal performance

$$\dot{Q}^{ST} = A^{ST} \eta_0^{ST} S^{pan} f^{ST} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{with} \quad f^{ST} = 0.97 - 0.0367 \left(\frac{a^*}{\eta_0^{ST}} \right) + 0.0006 \left(\frac{a^*}{\eta_0^{ST}} \right)^2,$$

using the panel area A^{ST} , the zero-loss panel efficiency η_0^{ST} , the solar radiation on the panel S^{pan} as in (4) and a collector performance factor f^{ST} , Murphy et al. (2011). Heat losses from the panel are considered using the performance factor f^{ST} , which depends on the type of panel. For this paper, evacuated tubes with $\eta_0^{ST} = 0.6$ and $a^* = 3$ are used.

2.2. Conversion units

The task of the conversion units is to provide the heat required for the industrial process using electricity or gas. There are a lot of ways to generate heat, e.g. using combined heat and power units, but firstly only the components described below were considered in this work. The thermal output \dot{Q}^{GB} of the gas boiler is calculated according to

$$\dot{Q}^{GB} = \dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB} \lambda^{GB} \quad (8)$$

with the nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB} and the load fraction λ^{GB} limited by lower and upper bounds $0.2 \leq \lambda^{GB} \leq 1.0$. The power P^{GB} required for

Fig. 2. (a) angles to calculate the solar radiation (b) efficiency η^{WT} of wind turbines depending on the wind load λ^{WT} and (c) efficiency η^{GB} of the gas boiler depending on the load fraction λ^{GB} .

generating \dot{Q}^{GB} is calculated based on the efficiency η^{GB} , so that the behavior in part load can also be considered, Sass et al. (2020):

$$P^{GB} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{GB}}{\eta^{GB}} \quad \text{with} \quad (9)$$

$$\eta^{GB} = \frac{21.754\lambda^{GB3} - 7.001\lambda^{GB2} + 1.397\lambda^{GB} - 0.076}{20.666\lambda^{GB3} - 5.342\lambda^{GB2} + 0.678\lambda^{GB} + 0.035} \eta_{nom}^{GB}$$

and a nominal efficiency of $\eta_{nom}^{GB} = 0.8$, Fig. 2c. In the calculation, λ^{GB} is set to $\lambda^{GB} = 0.2$ if $0.01 \leq \lambda^{GB} \leq 0.2$ to consider the lower bound and $\lambda^{GB} = 0.0$ if $\lambda^{GB} < 0.01$ to also consider the non-use of the gas boiler.

The electric boiler is calculated in the same way as the gas boiler. Thus, the thermal output \dot{Q}^{EB} is determined according to

$$\dot{Q}^{EB} = \dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB} \lambda^{EB} \quad (10)$$

with the nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB} and the load fraction $0.0 \leq \lambda^{EB} \leq 1.0$. In contrast to the gas boiler, the entire range of the nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB} can be used. Furthermore, a constant efficiency $\eta^{EB} = 0.95$ is assumed, so that a required power is calculated by

$$P^{EB} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{EB}}{\eta^{EB}} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{EB}}{0.95}. \quad (11)$$

Finally, heat pumps are also considered for the heat supply, as these offer the possibility of providing heat very efficiently and on the basis of renewable energy sources, especially in connection with thermal energy storages and solar thermal systems. The thermal output \dot{Q}^{HP} of the heat pump is also calculated by

$$\dot{Q}^{HP} = \dot{Q}_{nom}^{HP} \lambda^{HP} \quad (12)$$

with the nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{HP} and the load fraction λ^{HP} . As by the gas boilers, the load fraction is limited by an upper and lower bound, such that $0.2 \leq \lambda^{HP} \leq 1.0$. The efficiency of the heat pump is calculated according to Sass et al. (2020) as the product of a constant 2nd law efficiency $\eta_{2nd}^{HP} = 0.36$ and the Carnot efficiency η^{carnot} that serves as theoretical maximum:

$$\eta^{HP} = \frac{\eta_{2nd}^{HP}}{\eta^{carnot}} = \eta_{2nd}^{HP} \frac{T_{h,out}^{HP}}{T_{h,out}^{HP} - T_{c,in}^{HP}} \quad (13)$$

with the heat sink temperature $T_{h,out}^{HP}$ as output and the heat source temperature $T_{c,in}^{HP}$ as input of the heat pump. In (13) it becomes clear that a heat pump can work most effective when an appropriate high-quality heat source is available and the difference between $T_{h,out}^{HP}$ and $T_{c,in}^{HP}$ is as small as possible. The required electrical power P^{HP} of the heat pump is then determined by

$$P^{HP} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{HP}}{\eta^{HP}}. \quad (14)$$

In addition to a minimum temperature difference of $T_{h,out}^{HP} - T_{c,in}^{HP} \geq 25$ K, a maximum output temperature $T_{h,out}^{HP} \leq 160$ °C is also taken into account, Schlosser et al. (2020). Using (13) and (14) the required

thermal power \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP} taken from a connected thermal energy storage can be calculated for a given temperature difference:

$$\eta_{2nd}^{HP} \frac{T_{h,out}^{HP}}{T_{h,out}^{HP} - T_{c,in}^{HP}} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{HP}}{P^{HP}} = \frac{\dot{Q}^{HP}}{\dot{Q}^{HP} - \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP}} \quad (15)$$

$$\Rightarrow \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP} = \dot{Q}^{HP} \left(1 - \frac{T_{h,out}^{HP} - T_{c,in}^{HP}}{\eta_{2nd}^{HP} T_{h,out}^{HP}} \right).$$

Usually, only a constant efficiency of the heat pump is assumed during the design process. However, this means that solar thermal unit, thermal energy storage and heat pump are considered separately, which can lead to an incorrect evaluation of the overall system.

2.3. Thermal energy storage

The thermal energy storage is used to store the thermal output generated by e.g. the solar thermal unit and to make it available for the generation of the required heat. It is used on the one hand for preheating but also as a source for the heat pump, Fig. 3a. Starting from the currently stored thermal energy Q_0^{TES} , available thermal performance \dot{Q} during the considered time frame Δt is used to charge the storage tank

$$Q^{TES} = Q_0^{TES} + \dot{Q} \Delta t \quad \text{with} \quad Q^{TES} \leq Q_{nom}^{TES} \quad (16)$$

ensuring that the nominal capacity Q_{nom}^{TES} of storage is not exceeded. Due to the fact, only a hot water storage is used in this paper the temperature T^{TES} of the storage tank can be determined based on the stored thermal energy Q^{TES} , the storage mass m^{TES} , the specific heat capacity of the storage medium c_p^{TES} and initial temperature T_0^{TES} :

$$Q^{TES} = c_p^{TES} m^{TES} (T^{TES} - T_0^{TES}) \quad (17)$$

$$\Rightarrow T^{TES} = T_0^{TES} + \frac{Q^{TES}}{c_p^{TES} m^{TES}}.$$

When discharging the storage, a simple calculation as in (17) is not suitable, because with the discharging of the storage, the storage temperature reduces and according to (15) also the thermal power taken from the storage by the heat pump. In order to better describe the discharging, Fig. 3a, it is necessary to consider the power used for preheating \dot{Q}_{TES}^w and for the heat pump \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP} within a single formulation

$$\dot{Q}^{TES} = -\dot{Q}_{TES}^w - \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP} = -c_p^w \dot{m}^w (T^{TES} - \Delta T - T_{in}^w) + \dot{Q}^{HP} \left(\frac{T_{h,out}^{HP} - T^{TES}}{\eta_{2nd}^{HP} T_{h,out}^{HP}} - 1 \right) \quad (18)$$

where the source temperature for the heat pump is set to the storage temperature $T_{c,in}^{HP} = T^{TES}$ and the output temperature for the preheating is chosen to be $T_{out}^w = T^{TES} - \Delta T$ in order to ensure a pinch in the

Fig. 3. Description of the two options for discharging the storage (a) and discharging of the storage according to (22) using $m^{TES} = 1000$ kg, $c_p^{TES} = 4.19$ kJ/kg K, $T_0^{TES} = 15$ °C, $c_p^w = 4.19$ kJ/kg K, $\dot{m}^w = 1.0$ kg/s, $\dot{Q}^{HP} = 100$ kW and $T_{h,out}^{HP} = 100$ °C (b).

heat exchangers of ΔT . By rearranging (18), formulation

$$\dot{Q}^{TES} = \underbrace{\left[c_p^w \dot{m}^w (\Delta T + T_{in}^w) + \dot{Q}^{HP} \left(\frac{T_{h,out}^{HP}}{\eta_{2nd}^{HP} T_{h,out}^{HP}} - 1 \right) \right]}_{c_1} - \underbrace{\left[c_p^w \dot{m}^w + \frac{\dot{Q}^{HP}}{\eta_{2nd}^{HP} T_{h,out}^{HP}} \right]}_{c_2} T^{TES} \quad (19)$$

is obtained, where the terms in the square brackets, that are assumed to be constant with time, are summarized by the constants c_1 and c_2 . If the formulation of T^{TES} in (17) is used, Eq. (19) can be formulated such as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Q}^{TES} &= c_1 - c_2 T^{TES} = c_1 - c_2 \left(T_0^{TES} + \frac{Q^{TES}}{c_p^{TES} m^{TES}} \right) \\ &= \underbrace{c_1 - c_2 T_0^{TES}}_{c_3} - \underbrace{\frac{c_2}{c_p^{TES} m^{TES}}}_{c_4} Q^{TES} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

with the constants c_3 and c_4 , where (20) now depends on Q^{TES} . With this, the following problem can be formulated

$$\dot{Q}^{TES} = \frac{dQ^{TES}}{dt} = c_3 - c_4 Q^{TES} \implies \frac{dQ^{TES}}{c_3 - c_4 Q^{TES}} = dt \quad (21)$$

which can be solved by integrating separately from Q_0^{TES} to Q^{TES} and t_1 to t_2 , where $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$:

$$Q^{TES} = \left(-\frac{c_3}{c_4} + Q_0^{TES} \right) e^{-c_4 \Delta t} + \frac{c_3}{c_4} \quad (22)$$

Using (22), the energy provided by the storage $Q^{TES} - Q_0^{TES}$ and \dot{Q}_{TES}^w as well as \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP} can be calculated over different time ranges, taking into account the effect of (15) and the fact that also with decreasing storage temperature T^{TES} in the preheating less energy can be transferred, Fig. 3b. During the discharging of the thermal energy storage it is checked that $Q^{TES} \geq 0$.

2.4. Integration of the units

To model the entire energy concept of the industrial process, the components described in the previous chapter must be integrated to check whether the demand of the production process can be covered at any time. The heat requirement considered here corresponds to the batch process of an existing food processing process shown in Fig. 4a, whereby this is only applicable on weekdays, due to the fact that there is no production at off days. Here the day is divided into 7 sections,

with different time periods $\Delta t^{(i)}$ and heat requirements $\dot{Q}^{dem,(i)}$ with a peak load that is only required for a short period of time.

For the analysis of the system consisting of the described components with their nominal capacity, representative weeks are evaluated for each month of the year. This is necessary because the solar radiation and thus also the power of the PV and ST unit change greatly over the course of a year. To determine the daily solar radiation $S_{M,d}^{hor}$ for a specific month, the monthly values S_{M}^{hor} are divided by the corresponding number of days per month. The analysis of each week starts on Saturday with an empty thermal energy storage. This means that the storage can be charged over the weekend, since there is no heat demand for the production process here. In general, the charging level of the storage is calculated according to the sections in Fig. 4a by

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{TES,(i+1)} &= Q^{TES,(i)} - \left(\dot{Q}_{TES}^{w,(i)} + \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP,(i)} - \dot{Q}^{ST,(i)} \right) \Delta t^{(i)} \\ \text{w.r.t } Q^{TES,(i+1)} &\leq Q_{nom}^{TES} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where at weekends $\dot{Q}_{TES}^{w,(i)} = \dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP,(i)} = 0$. The terms used for the integration of the units, their meaning and the unit are summarized in Table 1. In order to determine $\dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP,(i)}$, according to (18) it is necessary to define the thermal output of the heat pump \dot{Q}^{HP} . Since the components in the batch process under consideration have to be operated at partial load, in sections with a lower heat demand $\dot{Q}^{dem,(i)}$ it is necessary to determine appropriate load fractions λ^{GB} , λ^{EB} and λ^{HP} of the units. In this paper, this is realized by a load optimization with regard to minimal operating costs:

$$\min_{\lambda \in L} f \quad \text{s.t.} \quad h^{(i)} = \dot{Q}^{dem,(i)} - \dot{Q}^{GB,(i)} - \dot{Q}^{EB,(i)} - \dot{Q}^{HP,(i)} - \dot{Q}_{TES}^{w,(i)} \leq 0 \quad (24)$$

with $f = p_{buy}^{el} E^{el,(i)} + p_{buy}^{gas} E^{gas,(i)}$, price for electricity p_{buy}^{el} and for natural gas p_{buy}^{gas} as well as

$$E^{el,(i)} = (P^{HP,(i)} + P^{EB,(i)}) \Delta t^{(i)}, \quad E^{gas,(i)} = P^{GB,(i)} \Delta t^{(i)}, \quad (25)$$

$$L = \left\{ \lambda = [\lambda^{GB}, \lambda^{EB}, \lambda^{HP}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid h^{(i)} \leq 0, \lambda^l \leq \lambda \leq \lambda^u \right\}. \quad (26)$$

Due to $h^{(i)} \leq 0$ it can be ensured that the heat demand of the production process is covered in each section i with minimal operational cost.

When calculating the required electrical energy $E^{el,(i)}$, the energy of the PV and WT unit is also taken into account, which is not required to cover the electricity demand of the production process. The total electricity demand of a day is then calculated according to

$$E_d^{el} = E_d^{BL} + E_d^{WL} - E_d^{PV} - E_d^{WT} + \sum_{i=1}^7 (P^{HP,(i)} + P^{EB,(i)}) \Delta t^{(i)} \quad (27)$$

with daily energy generated by the PV unit E_d^{PV} and the WT unit E_d^{WT} as well as daily base load E_d^{BL} and load E_d^{WL} on the working

Fig. 4. (a) considered batch process with daily heat demand sections i and (b) charging level of the thermal energy storage for one week in November and an exemplary energy concept.

days, which is needed e.g. to use the electrical machines. The daily gas demand is calculated according to

$$E_d^{gas} = \sum_{i=1}^7 P^{GB,(i)} \Delta t^{(i)} \quad (28)$$

The calculation of the daily demands is carried out consecutively for all days of the week. A negative energy demand means that more energy has been produced than is needed and this amount can be sold, a positive energy demand means that the corresponding amount has to be bought. The charging level of the storage is taken over from one day to the next, as shown exemplarily in Fig. 4b. Since representative weeks with five working days are analyzed for all months, a total of $4 \times 5 \times 12 = 240$ load optimizations (24) are required for the evaluation of each single energy concept.

3. Methodology of the deterministic energy concept optimization

The results of the analysis of the energy concept from Section 2.4 essentially depend on the dimensioning or the nominal capacities of the units used. For example, larger PV or WT units lead to a larger amount of electrical energy being produced, which, according to (27), can reduce the energy demand. Furthermore, a larger ST unit with a corresponding thermal energy storage means that, according to (23), the heat pump also has a high-temperature source available or the energy in the storage can be used for preheating, so that less additional energy is needed. In addition, the CO₂ emissions can also be reduced by using renewable energy sources like PV, WT and ST units, although an increase in the normal capacities is also associated with increased investment costs. In order to find suitable trade-offs between economic criteria such as costs and ecological criteria such as CO₂ emissions,

optimization processes are applied. Therefore, in the next section, the considered criteria will first be explained before the corresponding optimization problem is formulated and the optimization result is discussed.

3.1. Determination of the objectives

As already described, economic as well as ecological criteria are considered in the design process. The total annual costs TAC , which are calculated on the one hand from the required operating costs and on the other hand from the investment costs, are chosen as ecological criterion. The annual investment cost for each unit c^i , $i \in \{PV, WT, ST, GB, EB, HP, TES\}$ is determined according to

$$c^i = \left(\frac{(\beta + 1)^\tau \beta}{(\beta + 1)^\tau - 1} + \alpha^i \right) C^i \quad (29)$$

with $C^i = C^{i,0} \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{nom}^i / Q_{nom}^i / P_{nom}^i / A^i}{\dot{Q}_{nom}^{i,0} / Q_{nom}^{i,0} / P_{nom}^{i,0} / A^{i,0}} \right)^\gamma$

with total capital expenditure C^i for unit with nominal capacity $\dot{Q}_{nom}^i / Q_{nom}^i / P_{nom}^i / A^i$, cost $C^{i,0}$ and nominal capacity $\dot{Q}_{nom}^{i,0} / Q_{nom}^{i,0} / P_{nom}^{i,0} / A^{i,0}$ of a reference unit, scaling exponent γ , maintenance cost factor α^i and interest rate β as well as time horizon τ at financing, Smith (2005). Thus, in c^i the annual rate for financing is combined with the maintenance costs. The values used here for the individual units are summarized in Table 2, Sass et al. (2020) and Seitz et al. (2017).

To calculate the operating costs, days with positive and negative energy demand E_d^{el} must be considered separately. Thus, in $E_{in,m}^{el}$, all positive energy demands of the considered representative week of each month m are summarized and in $E_{out,m}^{el}$ all negative ones. For the

Table 1
Overview of key terms used in the unit integration.

Term	Description	Unit
Q^{TES}	thermal energy stored in the TES	kWh
\dot{Q}_{TES}^w	thermal output of the TES to preheat the water	kW
\dot{Q}_{TES}^{HP}	thermal output of the TES as heat pump source	kW
\dot{Q}^{ST}	thermal output of the ST used to load the TES	kW
\dot{Q}^{GB}	thermal output of the gas boiler	kW
\dot{Q}^{EB}	thermal output of the electric boiler	kW
\dot{Q}^{HP}	thermal output of the heat pump	kW
P^{EB}	electrical input of the electric boiler to generate \dot{Q}^{EB} ($\dot{Q}^{EB} < P^{EB}$)	kW
P^{GB}	input of natural gas to generate \dot{Q}^{GB} ($\dot{Q}^{GB} < P^{GB}$)	kW
P^{HP}	electrical input of the heat pump to generate \dot{Q}^{HP} ($\dot{Q}^{HP} > P^{HP}$)	kW
E_d^{BL}	daily electrical energy base demand of the industrial process (base load)	kWh
E_d^{WL}	daily electrical energy work demand of the industrial process (work load)	kWh
E_d^{PV}	electrical energy produced by the photovoltaic unit at one day	kWh
E_d^{WT}	electrical energy produced by the wind turbine unit at one day	kWh
E_d^{el}	daily electrical energy balance of the industrial process	kWh
E_d^{gas}	daily natural gas demand of the industrial process	kWh

Table 2
Values for calculating annual component costs c^i .

Unit	Reference capacity	CAPEX ⁰ /€	γ/-	α/-	τ/-	β/-
PV unit	$P_{nom}^{PV,0} = 1$ kW	1400	0.95	0.01	10	0.03
WT unit	$P_{nom}^{WT,0} = 1$ kW	5000	0.95	0.03	10	0.03
ST unit	$A^{ST,0} = 1$ m ²	240	0.95	0.5	10	0.03
GB unit	$\dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB,0} = 1$ kW	2700	0.45	0.015	10	0.03
EB unit	$\dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB,0} = 1$ kW	70	0.66	0.02	10	0.03
HP system	$P_{nom}^{HP,0} = 1$ kW	1650	0.95	0.02	10	0.03
TES system	$\dot{Q}_{nom}^{TES,0} = 1$ kWh	80	0.87	0.02	10	0.03

calculation of the weekly gas demand $E_{in,m}^{gas}$, however, the daily values E_d^{gas} are simply summed up. The total annual costs TAC as economic criteria can then be calculated:

$$TAC = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \left(p_{buy}^{el} E_{in,m}^{el} - p_{sell}^{el} E_{out,m}^{el} + p_{buy}^{gas} E_{in,m}^{gas} \right) 4.3 + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{J}} c^i \quad (30)$$

with $\mathcal{M} = \{Jan, Feb, \dots, Dec\}$, $\mathcal{J} = \{PV, WT, ST, GB, EB, HP, TES\}$, revenue for the sale $p_{sell}^{el} = 0.06$ €/kW and price for the purchase $p_{buy}^{el} = 0.35$ €/kW of electrical energy as well as price for natural gas $p_{buy}^{gas} = 0.13$ €/kW. The weekly values are multiplied by 4.3 to get estimated monthly values.

The global warming impact GWI is considered as environmental criterion

$$GWI = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \left(g^{el} \left(E_{in,m}^{el} - E_{out,m}^{el} \right) + g^{gas} E_{in,m}^{gas} \right) \quad (31)$$

with the specific global warming impacts $g^{el} = 349 g_{CO_2eq}$ /kWh and $g^{gas} = 244 g_{CO_2eq}$ /kWh of electricity and natural gas, respectively, [Sass et al. \(2020\)](#). It should be noted that the specific global warming impact from purchased energy is actually varying greatly over time, depending on the shares of e.g. renewable energies. Formulation (31) reduces the GWI through the purchase of energy to emphasize the positive contribution. It should be noted at this point that the manufacture of components or units also has an effect on the GWI , which, according to [Guillèn-Gosálbez \(2011\)](#), is significantly lower than that caused by operation. However, the contribution of manufacturing to the GWI is not considered here.

3.2. Optimization problem formulation

The two optimization objectives (30) and (31) depend on the one hand on the investment costs of the installed units and on the other hand on the consumption of electrical energy and natural gas. Both criteria therefore depend on the nominal capacities of the installed units, which are to be determined as part of an optimal design. Thus, the design parameters \mathbf{p}_{nom} of the energy concept are:

$$\mathbf{p}_{nom} = [A^{PV}, P_{nom}^{WT}, A^{ST}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{HP}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{TES}]^T. \quad (32)$$

The multi-objective optimization problem for minimizing both objectives, total annual cost TAC (30) and global warming impact GWI (31), simultaneously is

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}_{nom} \in P} \begin{bmatrix} TAC \\ GWI \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

$$\text{with } P = \left\{ \mathbf{p}_{nom} \in \mathbb{R}^7 \mid h_{max} \leq 0, \mathbf{p}'_{nom} \leq \mathbf{p}_{nom} \leq \mathbf{p}^u_{nom} \right\}$$

with the constraint $h_{max} = \max(h^{(i)})$, which equals to the maximum of all constraints h obtained by the load optimizations defined in (24). It can happen, that if the nominal capacities of the GB, EB and HP units are chosen too small, a feasible solution of (24) is not possible, which result in $h > 0$. This constraint is essential, since the units are chosen to be as small as possible, particularly to reduce the investment costs. Therefore, the additional constraint h_{max} ensures that the heat demand of the industrial process is covered at all times. The lower limits for the design parameters are chosen to be $\mathbf{p}'_{nom} = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T$ and

the upper limits to be $\mathbf{p}^u_{nom} = [4000, 24, 2000, 250, 250, 250, 5000]^T$. This means that the nominal capacity of the units considered in the optimized energy concept has to be between the lower and upper limits. Thus, individual units do not have to be used and the entire heat requirement can be covered by GB, EB or HP. The choice of upper limits for the PV and ST unit essentially depends on the space available. In general, the choice of limits can have an influence on the final solutions of the optimization, so it can be helpful to carry out several optimizations with different limits and to compare the results. It should be noted here that the capacity of the units is modeled continuously, so that the results may not be directly implemented in practice, since e.g. PV units are only available in a certain size. For practical applications, this would mean that smoothing (round to realizable capacities) would have to take place after the optimization, similar to topology optimizations. Alternatively, mixed integer algorithms with previously defined available capacities can also be used, which are able to handle integer and real numbers as design parameters. However, these algorithms usually have a more complex structure and therefore poorer convergence, [Schlueter et al. \(2009\)](#).

4. Methodology of the robust optimization approach

The result of the optimization (33) depend decisively on the assumptions about e.g. prices for electricity and gas, unit performances, investment costs as well as assumptions about environmental influences such as wind speeds and solar radiation. Uncertainties in these assumptions can lead to deviating and undesirable system behavior. It is the task of robust optimization to take this into account in the design process. In the following sections, the uncertainties assumed here are presented, the corresponding robust optimization concept is explained.

4.1. Description of uncertainties

In this paper uncertainties in the price of gas p_{buy}^{gas} and in the solar radiation S^{pan} on the panels are considered for a first investigation. This is realized in the form of two uncertainty factors f_1 and f_2 such that:

$$\tilde{S}^{pan} = S^{pan} f_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{p}_{buy}^{gas} = p_{buy}^{gas} f_2 \quad (34)$$

with $0.9 \leq f_1 \leq 1.0$ and $1.0 \leq f_2 \leq 2.0$. Thus, the gas price will change with an assumed increase of up to 100%. Solar radiation is assumed to be reduced by up to 10%, which corresponds to degraded panel performance, additional shading, or overestimation of solar radiation. In this first investigation, both uncertainties are considered simultaneously and uncorrelated. The range of the factor f_1 was initially chosen for demonstration purposes without any theoretical justification. The range of factor f_2 for the gas price is based on the actual increase in Germany due to the Ukrainian crisis and the associated shortages. However, both factors have a major influence on the economic efficiency of the industrial process and were therefore selected.

Local response surfaces are used to assess the influence of f_1 and f_2 on the optimization objectives (30) and (31), [Bestle et al. \(2011\)](#). Response surfaces enable the relationship between input parameters and output of a function to be approximated on the basis of a few function evaluations in order to subsequently carrying out extensive

statistical studies very efficiently. To set up the response surfaces, a random sample $[f_1^{(i)}, f_2^{(i)}]$, $i = 1(1)4$ based on a Latin Hypercube Sampling, Helton and Davis (2003), is defined and analyzed with $\mathbf{p}_{nom} = \mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1} = const.$ Kriging models \hat{y}_{TAC} and \hat{y}_{GWI} are then created using the calculated values of $TAC^{(i)}$ and $GWI^{(i)}$, Jones et al. (1998). The response surface \hat{y}_{TAC} is shown in Fig. 5a as an example. A random sample with $N = 1e3$ sampling points covering the entire range shown in Fig. 5a is then defined and evaluated just using the response surfaces in order to determine the robust criteria. The 95% quantiles P_{95}^{TAC} and P_{95}^{GWI} of the objectives are chosen as criteria, which e.g. for TAC is defined as follows:

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I(\hat{y}_{TAC}^{(i)}) = 0.95 \quad \text{with} \quad I(\hat{y}_{TAC}^{(i)}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \hat{y}_{TAC}^{(i)} \leq P_{95}^{TAC} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

and describes a value under which 95% of all elements of the sample are located. However, since the criteria were only determined on the basis of the response surfaces, the question arises as to how accurate these estimates were. For this purpose, the variances \hat{s}_{TAC} and \hat{s}_{GWI} of the Kriging estimates \hat{y}_{TAC} and \hat{y}_{GWI} can be used, Jones (2001). This allows to define lower and upper limits, e.g.

$$\hat{y}_{TAC}^{l,(i)} = \hat{y}_{TAC}^{(i)} - 3\hat{s}_{TAC}^{(i)} \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{y}_{TAC}^{u,(i)} = \hat{y}_{TAC}^{(i)} + 3\hat{s}_{TAC}^{(i)}, \quad (36)$$

which define a range in which the actual value $TAC^{(i)}$ is within a probability of $\approx 99.99\%$, Fig. 5b. With these lower and upper limits, the quantiles can then be determined according to (35) and thus a quantile range

$$R_{P,95}^{TAC} = P_{95}^{u,TAC} - P_{95}^{l,TAC} \quad (37)$$

can be estimated. If this range is above a 1% limit of P_{95}^{TAC} , the response surface has to be refined. Appropriate update points are defined by solving the optimization problem

$$\max_{f_1, f_2} \hat{s}_{TAC} \quad \text{with} \quad \hat{s}_{TAC} \quad \text{and} \quad 1.0 \leq f_2 \leq 2.0 \quad (38)$$

which finds the point where the estimation \hat{y}_{TAC} has the greatest variance \hat{s}_{TAC} . This update process is carried out until the quantile range (37) is sufficiently small, Fig. 5c and d. As can be seen, the response surface can thus be updated very efficiently using just a

few iterations. The choice of the 1% limit represents a compromise between the computational effort and the accuracy of the optimization results. When evaluating, it must be considered that results within this tolerance can no longer be distinguished. For optimizations to converge towards more accurate solutions, the tolerance must be reduced.

4.2. Robust optimization formulation

Due to the fact, that the robust assessment is performed according to the adaptive local response surface procedure described in the previous section, where a number of energy concept evaluations are needed for a single design, just a single objective robust optimization approach is chosen in order to reduce the computational effort. This results in the optimization problem to minimize the 95% quantile of TAC:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}_{nom} \in P} P_{95}^{TAC} \quad (39)$$

with

$$P = \left\{ \mathbf{p}_{nom} \in \mathbb{R}^7 \left[\begin{array}{l} P_{95}^{GWI} - P_{95,ref}^{GWI} \leq 0, \mathbf{p}_{nom}^l \leq \mathbf{p}_{nom} \leq \mathbf{p}_{nom}^u \end{array} \right] \right\},$$

where in addition to (33) a further constraint is added to ensure that an improvement of P_{95}^{TAC} is not achieved by an increase of P_{95}^{GWI} greater than a reference $P_{95,ref}^{GWI}$. This will ensure the comparability with the deterministic design optimization later in this paper. Without this additional constraint, a lower value P_{95}^{TAC} could be achieved by a higher value P_{95}^{GWI} and according to the concept of multi-objective optimization, both designs would be equally good or not comparable.

5. Discussion of optimization results

In this chapter, the result of the deterministic optimization is first discussed and a reference design for the robust optimization is selected. This is then compared with the result of the robust optimization. Based on this comparison, the advantages and limitations of robust optimizations are discussed and their field of application is described.

Fig. 5. Using (a) four and (c) eight design evaluations (black points) and the associated differences $\hat{y}_{TAC}^u - \hat{y}_{TAC}^l$ between upper and lower bound (b) and (d).

Fig. 6. (a) Pareto-front as solution of the multi-objective problem (33).

5.1. Result of the deterministic optimization

The deterministic multi-objective optimization problem (33) is solved by the genetic algorithm NSGA2, Deb et al. (2000), which is implemented like the modeling of the units and the energy concept in Python. This is a global evolutionary optimization algorithm, which usually requires a higher number of design evaluations due to its stochastic operations. These algorithms are therefore essentially used for evaluations with short computing times. With longer computing times, local optimization algorithms are increasingly used, which can quickly achieve improvements to an initial design, but may not reach the global optimum. The result of the multi-objective optimization is a Pareto-front consisting of optimal compromises between the objectives, Fig. 6. Here it can be clearly seen that the objectives TAC and GWI are contradictory and the design $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ for a minimum TAC causes only about half the annual costs as the design $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,2}$ for a minimum GWI. However, there are also compromises in between that can be chosen for implementation. The low TAC is realized mainly due to a low gas price p_{buy}^{gas} compared to the price of electricity p_{buy}^{el} and a high nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB} of the GB unit, while a low GWI is achieved through a high use of renewable energy sources, a large thermal energy storage and a high nominal capacity \dot{Q}_{nom}^{HP} of the HP unit. Based on the Pareto-front, optimal energy concepts can now be selected that meet economic and environmental aspects. For example, a concept with minimal TAC can be selected for a desired GWI. These optimizations can therefore make a decisive contribution to accelerating the restructuring of industrial processes. At this point it is important to mention that a different choice of p_{buy}^{gas} and p_{buy}^{el} would also have led to different optimal solutions. Therefore, it is important to make an appropriate choice as the basis for

optimization. This is usually quite difficult because industrial processes are operated over a long period of time and price developments cannot be properly predicted. Also, the results cannot be directly applied to other locations, as other environmental conditions such as temperatures and solar radiation would lead to other optimal energy concepts.

For further investigations the optimal design $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ of the deterministic optimization is chosen, because this concept requires the lowest annual costs and thus may an appropriate choice from an economic perspective. If the uncertainties described in Section 4.1 are applied, this results in the distributions of TAC and GWI shown in Fig. 7. To compute the distributions, local response surfaces were built around the design $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$. Then an uncorrelated, uniformly distributed random sample with the size of $N = 1e3$ was evaluated using the response surfaces at the entire range of the assumed uncertainties f_1 and f_2 as defined in (34). Additionally, the quantiles $P_{95,det*,1}^{TAC}$ and $P_{95,det*,1}^{GWI}$ are determined for the design $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ using the updated response surfaces. As can be seen from the distribution in Fig. 7a, a TAC of 175k€ is only achieved in the ideal case. If there are deviations from the assumptions of the deterministic optimization, major changes can occur. Thus, within the assumed uncertainties the spread in the TAC covers a range of 30k€. The spread of the GWI comes mainly from the factor f_1 , which results in an increased consumption of natural gas, Fig. 7b. But the factor f_2 also has an influence on the GWI, since an increased gas price p_{buy}^{gas} can lead to an increased use of HP and EB as result of the operational optimization (24), which can lead to an increased GWI due to the specific global warming impacts used. In any case, after deterministic optimization, it should be checked whether deviations in the optimization assumptions can lead to undesirable values of the objectives.

Fig. 7. Frequency distributions of the optimal solution $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ with respect to (a) TAC and (b) GWI.

Fig. 8. Frequency distributions of the optimal solutions $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ (grey) and \mathbf{p}_{nom}^{rob*} (dark grey) with respect to (a) TAC and (b) GWI.

5.2. Comparison of deterministic and robust optimization results

The robust optimization problem (39) is solved using a differential evolution algorithm, Storn and Price (1997), implemented in Python, whereby the computing time was approximately twice as high as with the deterministic multi-objective optimization (33). In contrast to multi-objective optimization, the result is not a set of optimal compromises but a single optimal design:

$$\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{rob*} = [A^{PV}, P_{nom}^{WT}, A^{ST}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{GB}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{EB}, \dot{Q}_{nom}^{HP}, Q_{nom}^{TES}]^T \tag{40}$$

$$= [3539.7, 0.3, 173.7, 3.5, 57.6, 161.9, 755.3]^T$$

Compared to the deterministic optimum $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$, Fig. 5, the TES and the ST unit were significantly increased and the nominal capacity of the GB unit was reduced to a small value. According to the selected robust criterion, the quantile value P_{95}^{TAC} and thus the high costs to be expected could be reduced, Fig. 8a. However, over a wide range, the deterministic optimum $\mathbf{p}_{nom}^{det*,1}$ results in low TAC, whereas the robust optimum has a significantly smaller variance in the TAC. In any case, the robust optimum \mathbf{p}_{nom}^{rob*} results in a significantly smaller GWI, Fig. 8b, which was not a goal of the optimization but is an effect due to an increase in the share of renewable energies. The choice of a specific objective of the robust optimization or the desired properties of the energy concept depend heavily on individual factors and must be redetermined depending on the situation.

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6. Conclusions

In this paper, the modeling of units of an energy concept was described and the procedure for the integrated analysis with regard to economic and environmental criteria was explained. Based on the analysis, a deterministic multi-objective and a robust single-objective optimization problem for the dimensioning of the units used were defined and corresponding optimizations were carried out.

It turns out that the results of the deterministic optimization depend strongly on the assumptions and boundary conditions used and deviations can lead to a large scatter in the objective functions. Furthermore,

changes in the boundary conditions of the optimization can lead to different optimal configurations. As part of a robust optimization, assumptions about uncertainties in the price of natural gas and the solar radiation were considered and a design was found that has a lower scatter in the TAC and reduces the expected high costs compared to a selected reference design from the deterministic multi-objective optimization. This shows that the consideration of uncertainties is particularly necessary for long planning periods.

Just as important as identifying the advantages and achievements is considering the limitations. Essentially, the result of the described robust optimization depends on the assumptions about uncertainties and the formulation of the robust optimization objectives. Thus, in this paper, simple assumptions are made about correlation and spread of the uncertainties, so that the results of this work only serve to demonstrate the methodology. In order to reduce the computing time, only a single, very conservative objective was used for the robust optimization, whereas two criteria are usually required to characterize statistical distributions: measures of central tendency and the spread. In order to find and discuss suitable compromises, individual objectives must be selected together with the operator or owner of the industrial plant. Furthermore, the units are modeled using simplified mathematical formulations, whereby no temperature-dependent and transient effects are considered. Thus, the results of optimizations described in this paper only serve as a starting point for analyses or optimizations using more detailed unit simulations.

According to the limitations described above, realistic spreads and correlations of the uncertainties have to be defined in future studies. For example, price developments and scenarios from previous years or decades can be used for this purpose. Furthermore, the effects of different robust criteria on the optimal solutions are investigated and discussed. In order to finally carry out multi-objective robust optimizations, further investigations are necessary to accelerate the robust assessments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael Lockan: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Rushit Kansara:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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